

Synthesis of cross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol) and investigation of its efficiency in removing lead ion from aqueous solution

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Abstract : Cross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol) has been synthesized for the investigation of its efficiency in removing lead ion from aqueous solution. The physical and chemical nature of the synthesized ion exchange resin has been elucidated with the help of chemical test, FTIR, SEM, TGA and DSC. Particle size (0.25 mm), surface area (80.2 m²/g), ion exchange capacity (3.2 meq H⁺/g), optimum pH (4.5), time (60 min) and temperature (40 °C) for Pb^{II} adsorption were determined. Metal ion adsorption kinetics, isotherms and thermodynamics have been studied.

Keywords : Cross-linking, lead ion, adsorption, isotherm, ion exchange.

Introduction

In the present decade, several researchers^{1,2} are engaged in synthesizing suitable polymers having selective metal ion binding capacity. Very few of them^{3,4} reported removal and recovery of lead ion from aqueous solutions using polymers. There are some works⁵⁻⁷ on uncross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol) and its analytical application as selective extractor for lead ions. However, there are no reports on the synthesis of PVA in presence of cross-linker and its application in removing lead ion from aqueous solution. Cross-linked PVA is expected to have better lead ion-binding capacity with faster kinetics than that of uncross-linked one. PVA is a cheaper and its physico-chemical properties can be enhanced by cross-linking.

The present work deals with the new procedure for removing lead(II) ion from aqueous solution using chemically synthesized cross-linked PVA. Under the sorption conditions, kinetic and thermodynamic parameters are evaluated. Different adsorption isotherms have been studied.

Experimental

Materials :

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (Burgoyne Burbidges, India; mol. wt. = 16100, degree of hydrolysis = 98.5–99.0 mol%, viscosity = 30 cps) was used, glutaraldehyde (sp. gravity = 1.06, S.d. fine chem. Ltd., India; mol. wt. = 100.12), lead nitrate (Merck, India) and sulfuric acid (Merck, India, 98% sp. gravity = 1.84, mol. wt. = 98.08) were used as received.

Synthesis of cross-linked PVA :

Cross-linking of PVA was carried out in a two-necked round-bottomed flask at 70 °C. A definite amount of PVA (0.5 g) was mixed with water (20 ml) and heated for 15 min. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. After an hour glutaraldehyde (0.1 g) was mixed to cross-link the PVA. Quenching with hydroquinone arrested cross-linking reaction after 1 h. The precipitated cross-linked polymer was separated by filtration and washed several times with 1 : 10 H₂SO₄ (v/v). The un-reacted PVA were separated by prolonged (24 h) extraction with water in a Soxhlet apparatus. Finally, the sample was extracted with acetone for 72 h to dissolve all other impurities. The colorless product was dried under vacuum at 100 °C for 72 h to a constant weight. The dried solid was grounded and screened through a set of sieves for the particles of the size ranged between 0.15 to 0.25 mm for conducting experiments.

Sorption and desorption procedure :

Adsorption and desorption was carried out by batch method⁸. One ml solution of the sample was withdrawn each time from the reaction mixture by a syringe at a gap of fixed time interval and analyzed for the study of adsorption kinetic. For isothermal study, the system was agitated for 60 min at a particular temperature and pH and then filtered for the analysis of residual metal ion complex metrically. The selectivity of the prepared resin among various metal ions (Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}; commonly found in electroplating waste) was determined. Resin

sample (0.013 g) was equilibrated for 60 min with 10 ml solution (3.3 ml of each metal ion solution, which contained 0.001 mole metal ion). The adsorbed metal ions were sequentially eluted with the selective stripping agents.

All the experiments were performed at least in triplicate at room temperature (27 °C). The adsorption capacity (Q , mg/g), percentage of recovery (R), cross-link density (q) was calculated from the following relations⁶⁻⁸.

$$Q = W_1/W_2 \quad (1)$$

$$R = W_3 \times 100/W_4 \quad (2)$$

$$q = M_0/M_c \quad (3)$$

where W_1 = metal adsorbed (mg), W_2 = adsorbent added (g), W_3 = metal ion eluted (g), W_4 = metal ion originally bound in the polymer (g), M_0 = molecular weight of the repeating unit, M_c = average molecular mass between consecutive cross-link⁹.

Results and discussion

Evidence for the formation of cross-linking polymer :

FTIR (Shimadzu 8400s) spectra of the cross-linked PVA exhibits all the characteristic peaks of PVA¹⁰ and four new peaks at 3857, 3838, 1720 and 1110 cm^{-1} . The peaks at 3857 and 3838 cm^{-1} are mainly due to the presence of moisture¹¹ in the sample. The TGA and DTA traces of the sample also indicate the presence of moisture. The bands at 1720 and 1110 cm^{-1} are probably due to carbonyl (C=O) stretching¹² of an aldehyde and ether

linkage (C-O-C)¹². Thus FTIR spectra confirms the cross-linking of PVA through incomplete conversion of aldehyde group (-CHO) of glutaraldehyde into ether linkage (-CH-O-).

The surface area of cross-linked polymer was determined by methylene blue adsorption method¹³ and was found to be 80.2 m^2/g . Average molecular weight between two consecutive cross-link, cross-link density and pore size of the material were 1335.6 g mol^{-1} , 0.053 and 67.73 Å respectively. Fig. 1 shows the scanning electron image of the synthesized polymer recorded at 10000X, which shows that surface of the polymer are not homogeneous and contains several pores. Fig. 2 shows the traces of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the polymer indicate that there are

Fig. 1. SEM photograph of the cross-linked PVA.

Fig. 2. TGA and DTA traces of the cross-linked PVA.

three steps weight loss. First step (40–60 °C, ≈30%), second step (200–210 °C, ≈40%) and third step weight losses (>220 °C, ≈25%) of the polymer due to removal of water, carbon dioxide, nitrogen and impurities respectively IDT (initial decomposition temperature) and FDT (final decomposition temperature) are found to be 40 and 248 °C respectively. The endothermic peak around 248 °C may be due to melting of the polymer.

The effect of sorbate dose (Pb^{II} concentration) on adsorption, keeping the other conditions (pH = 4.5, temperature = 27 °C, sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L and time = 1 h) fixed, was studied (Fig. 3). It was observed that lead ion uptake capacity of the sorbent increases sharply with the increase of metal ion concentration. The lead ion reten-

Fig. 3. Effect of sorbate dose on its adsorption (Sorbent dose = 1.3 mg/L, sorbate dose = 207 mg/L, time = 1 h, temperature = 27 °C, pH = 4.5).

tion capacity of the resin was 11.0 mg/g at low level of sorbate (207 ppm) and became 47.6 mg/g at 1000 ppm of lead. Uncross-linked PVA showed inferior results⁶.

The adsorption capacities were found to be 0.0978, 0.0716 and 0.0604 mmol/g for lead, nickel and cadmium ions respectively (Table 1). The order of affinity under competitive condition was the same as that obtained for single ion solutions (i.e. Pb^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cd^{II}). Nickel, cadmium and lead ions were eluted sequentially and quantitatively from the resin by 0.002 M H₂SO₄, 0.1 M H₂SO₄ and 0.01 M HNO₃ respectively. The stability constants ($K_{\text{stability}}$) for the various metal/resin complexes were in-

Table 1. Competitive adsorption and elution of Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions

Metal ions	Metal ions adsorbed (mg/g of polymer)	Metal ions adsorbed (mmol/g of polymer)	Eluent used	Eluent vol. (ml)	Recovery (%)
Ni ^{II}	3.8	0.0716	0.002 M H ₂ SO ₄	20	84
Cd ^{II}	6.8	0.0604	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20	78
Pb ^{II}	20.25	0.0978	0.1 M HNO ₃	40	96.25

Sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L, pH = 4.5, temp. = 27 °C, time = 1 h.

vestigated with Ruzic¹⁴ method. The $K_{\text{stability}}$ values for the complexes were 814, 614 and 216 L/mol for Pb^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} respectively. Better adsorption of lead ion is consistent with its higher stability constant.

The results (Fig. 4) have indicated that ~94% adsorption took place in 30 min, and the time required to reach the equilibrium is 60 min. The obtained equilibrium time is much less than reported values¹⁵ of other adsorbents.

Fig. 4. Variation of adsorption with time at different temperature (Sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L, sorbate dose = 207 ppm, pH = 4.5, time = 1 h : (1) 5 °C, (2) 27 °C, (3) 40 °C).

The time dependent experimental adsorption data are used to fit^{16,17} various kinetic models by linear regression plots. The equations¹⁸ used for fitting the data are : first order, pseudo-first order, second order, pseudo-second order, Bhattacharya-Venkobachor, power function and simple Elovich models. The present kinetic data could be best described by first order model : $-\ln(C/C_0) = k_1 t$ (C_0 and C denote concentration of lead ion at $t = 0$ and t

= t respectively; k_1 refers first order rate constant, min^{-1}). The plot of $-\ln(C/C_0)$ against t gives rise to straight line with very good correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.995, 0.990$ and 0.996 at $5, 27$ and 40 °C respectively).

Adsorption isotherm :

Five isotherms¹⁹ (Langmuir, Freundlich, Redlich and Temkin) were used for fitting the experimental data (Fig. 5). The isotherm data have been analyzed using the linear equation of various models (Table 2). Among isotherms, the order of fitting the experimental data at 27

Fig. 5. Adsorption isotherm of lead (Sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L, sorbate dose = 207 ppm, pH = 4.5 , time = 1 h : (1) 5 °C, (2) 27 °C, (3) 40 °C).

Table 2. Isotherm model and related statistical parameter

Isotherm model	Parameter	5 °C	27 °C	40 °C	
Langmuir (linear form)	R^2	0.983	0.992	0.982	
$C_e/Q_e = 1/K_a \cdot Q_m + C_e/Q_m$	K_a	0.00217	0.00022	0.000347	
	Q_m	110	132.8	156.6	
Freundlich (linear form)	R^2	0.955	0.974	0.985	
$\log Q_e = \log K_F + (1/n) \log C_e$	$1/n$	0.68	0.71	0.781	
	K_F	0.8	0.98	1.0	
Temkin	R^2	0.996	0.986	0.966	
$Q_e = a + 2.303 b \log C_e$	a	-52.2	-60.1	-62.2	
	b	14.4	18.02	20.1	
	R^2	0.995	0.990	0.984	
Redlich-Peterson (linear form)	R^2	0.995	0.990	0.984	
	$C_e/Q_e = 1/\alpha + (\beta/\alpha)C_e^\gamma$	α	0.242	0.329	0.407
		β	0.0050	0.0068	0.0072
		γ	0.900	0.900	0.900
Dubinn-Redushkevick	R^2	0.90	0.880	0.855	
$\ln Q_e = \ln Q'_m - K_{DR} e^2$	Q'_m	38.4	40.25	42.75	
	K_{DR}	0.0008	0.0005	0.0002	
$\epsilon = RT \ln(1 + 1/C_e)$					

°C is : Langmuir ($R^2 = 0.992$) > Redlich-Peterson ($R^2 = 0.990$) > Temkin ($R^2 = 0.986$) > Freundlich ($R^2 = 0.974$) > Dubinn-Redushkevick ($R^2 = 0.880$).

The effect of temperature on Pb^{II} adsorption at various sorbate dose is shown in Fig. 5. The adsorption capacity increases with the increasing temperature from 5 to 40 °C and then decreases with further increase of temperature. Initial increase of temperature favors the adsorption, while increase of temperature above 40 °C accelerates the desorption process.

Thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change (ΔG^0), enthalpy changes (ΔH^0) and entropy changes (ΔS^0) were calculated to evaluate the thermodynamic feasibility of the process and to confirm the nature of adsorption process. The Van't Hoff equation (eq. (4)) could be used for the estimation of thermodynamic parameters (ΔH^0 and ΔS^0) and ΔG^0 may be calculated through eq. (5).

$$\ln(Q_e/C_e) = (\Delta S^0/R) - \Delta H^0/RT \tag{4}$$

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0 \tag{5}$$

The value of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot of $\ln(Q_e/C_e)$ versus $1/T$. The negative values of ΔG^0 confirm the spontaneous nature and feasibility of the sorption process. The enthalpy change (ΔH^0) values are found to be $+10.80$ kJ/mol that indicated the endothermic nature of adsorption process.

Conclusion :

The synthesized resin adsorbs lead ion and it has good chemical and thermal stability. The ion exchange bed could be used more than 38 cycles with little loss of exchange capacity. The developed technique could be applied for the selective extraction of lead(II) from environmental samples. The proposed method is highly efficient, cost effective, simple and rapid. The cross linked polymer of PVA and glutaraldehyde has significantly higher lead ion uptake capacity and selectivity than that of uncross-linked PVA. The synthesized exchanger has strong affinity with lead ion over nickel and cadmium ions. The adsorption process follows the first order kinetics and Langmuir adsorption isotherm model.

Nomenclature

n : Freundlich constant	capacity (mg/g)
PVA : Poly(vinyl alcohol)	(dimensionless)
Sorbate : Lead ion	K_F : Freundlich
Sorbent : Cross-linked polyvinyl alcohol	constant (mg/g)
Q_t : Metal ion adsorption capacity at time t	a, b : Temkin constant
Q_e : Metal ion adsorption capacity at equilibrium	α, β, γ : Redlich-Peterson isotherm constant (L/mg)
C_0 : Initial metal ion concentration	Q'_m : Dubinin-Radushkevick constant related to adsorption capacity (mg/g)
C_e : Metal ion concentration at equilibrium	K_{DR} : Dubinin-Radushkevick adsorption constant (mol^2/KJ^2)
K_a : Langmuir constant (L/mg)	ϵ : Polyani potential related to mono-layer
Q_m : Langmuir constant related to mono-layer	

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